

Data* from: In-situ investigation of precipitation kinetics and microstructural evolution during friction extrusion of the aluminium alloy AA7075

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General Information

This repository contains all raw data and processed fitting outputs from SAXS/WAXS associated with the research published in:

E. Mathew et al., *Journal of Materials Processing Technology* (2026).

DOI: [10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2026.119303](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2026.119303)

The dataset is organized by the characterization techniques used in the study. Each folder contains the corresponding raw data referenced in the publication. FE thermocouple temperature measurements, hardness testing, transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) experiments were conducted at Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon. In-situ small- and wide-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS/WAXS) experiments were carried out at the PETRA III P07 beamline at DESY (Hamburg, Germany), operated by Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon under proposal I-20230278. Overall research investigation and coordination were performed at Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon.

Folder Structure

- **FE_process_parameter/**
Contains raw data for friction extrusion process parameters. Details regarding nomenclature and processing conditions are provided in a `README.txt` file.
- **FE_thermocouple_temperature/**
Contains raw temperature measurements for the two processes. Details regarding nomenclature and files are provided in a `README.txt` file.
- **WAXS/**
Contains raw WAXS data organized into two subfolders: `FE-16/` and `FE-22/`. A detailed `README.txt` file is provided within this folder.
- **SAXS/**
Contains detector images and transmission data from in-situ SAXS measurements. The directory

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is organized into subfolders FE-16/ and FE-22/. It also includes subfolders for calibration (`air/`, `air+window/`, and `Glasy_carbon/`) and a dedicated `Transmission/` log subfolder. A detailed `README.txt` file is provided within this folder.

- **Optical_microscope/**
Contains raw images for both FE-16 and FE-22 samples. Details regarding subfolders and files are provided in a `README.txt` file.
- **TEM/**
Contains raw TEM images. Organized into three subfolders: FE-16/, FE-22/, and Base material. Details regarding nomenclature and files are provided in a `README.txt` file.
- **SEM-EBSD/**
Contains raw scanning electron microscopy and electron backscatter diffraction (SEM-EBSD) data for both processes in the subfolders FE-16/ and FE-22/, respectively. Nomenclature and file descriptions are detailed in the accompanying `README.txt` file.
- **Hardness_data/**
Contains raw hardness data for both FE-16 and FE-22 samples. Information on subfolders and file structures is detailed in the `README.txt` file.

Citation

If you use any part of this dataset, please cite the associated publication:

E. Mathew et al., *Journal of Materials Processing Technology* (2026)

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